

2-SHO‘BA. ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOG KADRLARNING UZLUKSIZ KASBIY RIVOJLANISHINI TA‘MINLASH ISTIQBOLLARI.

ENGLISH TEACHING METHODOLOGIES FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION

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Teaching methodologies. Before introducing the different English Teaching Methodologies, (ETM), some concepts must be understood: Edward Anthony (as cited in Richard & Rodgers, 1986) described an approach as a set of correlative assumptions, evident or obvious, that deal with the nature of the matter to be taught. He explains that in the use of an approach to teach a language, there can be many plans for the presentation of the language materials in a procedural way; he refers to these plans as methods. Therefore, within one approach there can be many methods. Furthermore, Edward Anthony describes the technique as the implementation of the method in the classrooms, and the actions that would take place in the classroom.

On the other hand, Richard and Rodgers (1986), believe that as method is related theoretically to one approach, it is organized and determined by a **design** and then put into practice using a **procedure**. This whole broad relationship between theory and practice should be referred to as a **method**. The difference between an approach and a method is the emphasis and priority they give to the content versus instructional issues (Richard & Rodgers, 1986), i.e. "an approach is an idea or a concept, whereas a method is the procedures to turn that idea into reality in the classroom".

Second Language Acquisition. When the ETP aims at teaching English as a Second Language (ESL), it should be taken into account the route and the rate of the student's progress. The **route** is the nature of the stages students go through in the *acquisition* process, not taking into account their mother tongue nor the context of their learning, and the **rate** is the speed of the language's *learning* (Myles, 2011).

For this reason, regarding the Second Language Acquisition process (SLA), Myles (2011) believes that teachers should be more concerned about their student's **rate** of learning due to the implied pedagogical issues. Teachers need to observe what makes their students understand and learn the language faster and their capacities at certain stages of their development. From this, they will be able to adapt the **route** of learning and choose the most appropriate methodologies according to the situation and conditions (Myles, 2011)

Learning or acquiring a language? In the English Teaching Process (ETP), it is important to consider whether one method is aiming at acquiring or learning the language.

Stephen Krashen (1982) stated that the process of **acquiring** a language happens in a natural way, when children are immersed into a language, reacting spontaneously and interacting subconsciously. On the contrary, language **learning** is a conscious, rather rational process which normally happens in a programmed way, for example, when learning grammar or vocabulary.

Therefore, when learning English in the early stages, students begin to **acquire** the language unconsciously motivated by necessities, such as to get the attention of the teacher, to exchange information or to participate in a game. Consequently, children would start to understand, feel comfortable, and get used to an English speaking environment.

However, later on, when reaching Primary and higher levels of education, it is adequate for students to also **learn** English by means of studying the language using more complex approaches, learning the grammar, etc. (as native English speakers also do), but it is fundamental not to leave the acquisition process behind.

Which is the best method? According to Taylor (n.d.) linguists have demonstrated that there is not one single best method for everyone in all contexts, and that no teaching method is inherently superior to the others. In addition, it is not always possible, nor appropriate, to apply the same methodology to all learners.

It is very important for teachers and learners to understand the different methodologies. Moreover, when choosing the best one, several factors have to be taken into account, such as the age, objectives, environment, learning styles, needs, context, previous knowledge, mother tongue, aptitudes, backgrounds, ambitions, attitude, and even the length and the time of the lessons. It also implies encouragement, dedication, time and effort.

Total Physical Response. Children are constantly moving and willing to play. The Total Physical Response (TPR) method emphasizes the importance of aural comprehension, where students participate actively responding to certain commands. For example, "Close your eyes", "Touch your nose", "Sit down", etc. (Richards & Rodgers, 1986).

Using TPR activities in the ECE classroom promotes children being physically active. The procedures in the designs of this method would look like activities and games that are motivating and enjoyable methods to teach and acquire the English language. TPR activities can be done individually by asking individual children for commands while the rest of their classmates listen and process the information, or it could be done in groups. In the course of my student teacher field practice, this was the most used methodology and the one children seemed to enjoy the most.

White paper project. The White paper project, created by Ana García de la Fuente, director of the Art and visual Program at "Colegio San Patricio", has the purpose of teaching a second language in an enjoyable and simple way, reaching a personalized education. It is based on the Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) methodology, and its goals in ECE is to develop English oral comprehension and the artistic language as a way of letting children express themselves in a bilingual setting while enjoying talking about themselves and reinforcing the teacher-student bonding.

The White paper project consists of three activities directed to the acquisition, not the learning, of the language as a result of a natural communication between teacher and students. The activities consist of three parts. First, a group conversation where the teacher and students talk about a topic of interest, developing the general communicative competence in listening and talking. During the conversation, the students associate the information given with their previous knowledge. They structure their ideas and share them along with knowledge and even feelings and emotions. Secondly, the students would do an individual free drawing, finding a way of

transmitting their ideas, feeling and thoughts. It was observed that during the first months the drawings were rather simple but the more they used this methodology, the more the students realised the teacher cares to learn about them, and gave more importance to their drawings, adding more details and creativity. Thirdly, the One-to-One conversation takes place. It is an interaction between the teacher and the student talking in English about the drawing. It is a very important educational moment which can be reflected on and encourages English language speaking and comprehension skills, and their individual learning construction process, as well as learning about their innate capabilities, their experiences, feelings, personality, likes, concerns, and friends and family situations. (Salinas, 2016).

Conclusions. There is no one best method, but instead, in this progression scheme, methodologies should change and evolve as the child progresses. Normally, different methodologies should be used during the different school years and according to different backgrounds. Teachers should evaluate the route and rate of the learning process in order to choose, develop or adapt any available methodology.

Eclecticism was identified as the most versatile and useful approach to design and implement proper methodologies. When implementing the selected procedures is important to gather the ideas delivered by the children, and at the same time make them feel that the activities they are conducting are the result of their proposals, for motivational purposes.

Methodologies change over time, and should change according to the results of new researches, the evolution of new technologies, and, more importantly, the cognitive evolution of the child.

Some methodologies used for education in the native language, such as PBL or Learning by Projects, among others, may also be used as a methodology in the process of teaching a foreign language. We should not be limited to foreign language methodologies but also adapt other educational methodologies used for the native language.

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